

Sclerotia number per litre surface soil and diseased plants per 0.3 m² from fields with a history of ShB infection in Arkansas.

Variety	Year	Field	Position ^a	Samples (no.)	Sclerotia/litre			Diseased plants ^b /0.3 m ²		Field elevation (cm)
					Minimum	Maximum	Average	Maximum	Average	
STBN	1980	1		53	1	81	16.7	18	6.8	36
STBN		2		40	4	29	12.8	28	8.7	
STBN		3		96	3	33	12.3	20	2.0	
STBN		4		30	7	66	21.5	20	7.8	
STBN	1981	1		80	5	46	21.0	14	0.7	30
STBN		2		50	0	22	7.0	10	0.6	
Mars		3		80	2	36	20.6	10	1.2	
Mars		4		80	0	22	5.7	18	2.0	
Mars		5		60	0	7	1.5	0	0	
STBN		6		80	0	85	32.2	33	14.7	
STBN	1982	1	a	45	5	56	25.5	28	4.4	90
STBN		1	b	45	0	20	4.1	28	4.4	

^a = sclerotia in soil sample; b = sclerotia floating in water; STBN = Starbonnet. ^b Minimum no. was zero.

Material retained in the 0.50-mm mesh sieve was removed to a 250-ml plastic beaker, flooded onto another 0.50-mm mesh sieve, and washed and collected on filter paper in a Buchner funnel. Sclerotia were separated from debris and other fungal sclerotia by size, color, shape, and texture.

In 1982, floating sclerotia also were collected with all floating material within a 0.3-m² area using a fine-mesh screen. The material was poured onto filter paper and examined for presence of sclerotia.

When rice headed, disease incidence for each sample site was determined by counting the plants with ShB symptoms within 0.3 m².

Sclerotia population per litre of soil and number of diseased plants per 0.3 m² are in the table. In all fields surveyed in 1980 and 1982, higher sclerotia populations matched field margins. Three of four fields in 1980 and four of six in 1981 had more sclerotia at lower elevations.

Similarly, sites with many diseased plants had many sclerotia per 0.3- m² area. There were some exceptions, however. In 1980, one field with many sclerotia at a low elevation site had high disease incidence at high elevation but within the field edges. In 1981, a field with many sclerotia at a high elevation site had high disease incidence at low elevations.

When the number of diseased plants per 0.30 m² was regressed on the number of sclerotia per litre of soil for

individual fields, no relationship was detected. However, when a regression was calculated among fields (with an average for each field), correlation coefficient was 0.15 in 1980 and 0.45 in 1981. No relationship was detected in 1982 when diseased plants per 0.30 m² was regressed with floating sclerotia per litre of soil and floating sclerotia per 0.3-m² water surface area.

Distribution of *Rhizoctonia solani* sclerotia and diseased rice plants followed a general pattern. There were more sclerotia and diseased plants at low elevations in each field. Because water flows from high to low elevation within fields and from levee gates to the whole length and width of bays during first flooding, it may be that the flow

pattern carries sclerotia to low elevations and field margins. Spring storms and temporary flooding for soybean cultivation could cause similar results.

Soil was sampled before permanent flooding, and disease was rated at 2-cm internode elongation. Therefore, floating sclerotia could have moved in floodwater, thus resulting in the lack of relationship between average sclerotia per litre of soil and average diseased plants per 0.3 m². It may be for the same reason that there is no relationship between number of floating sclerotia and diseased plants. The fact that some fields had high inoculum concentration and few infected plants and vice versa may be due to differences in biotic and abiotic factors among fields. *ℵ*

Standardized test tube inoculation for bakanae disease (Bak)

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We attempted to standardize test tube inoculation for rapidly screening rice varieties for resistance to Bak caused by *Fusarium moniliforme*. Susceptible BR1 was used in two experiments to standardize spore concentration and seed-soaking duration. A sterile-water control was maintained in both experiments.

Twelve spore concentrations were evaluated (Table 1). Seeds were soaked

Table 1. Effect of spore concentration of *Fusarium moniliforme* on shoot and root elongation in rice, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.

Spore cone (thousand/ml)	Mean shoot length (cm)		Mean root length (cm)
0.0	6.4	e	4.5 ab
0.6	6.2	e	4.6 ab
1.2	6.4	e	4.9 a
1.8	6.4	e	4.5 ab
2.5	6.6	e	4.3 ab
3.0	7.1	de	4.9 a
6.0	8.5	d	4.8 a
31.0	10.7	c	5.5 a
62.0	12.5	b	5.0 a
125.0	15.2	a	4.5 ab
250.0	15.3	a	3.4 b
500.0	11.5	bc	0.9 c
LSD at 5%	1.3		1.2
CV (%)	8.1		17.0

for 48 h and 10 sprouted seeds were placed in each test tube and inoculated with 5 drops of the spore suspensions.

In experiment 2, seeds were soaked for 0, 24, 48, 72, or 96 h, and inoculated as above with a 125×10^3 spores/ml suspension (Table 2). Shoot and root length were recorded 7 d after inoculation with different spore concentrations and 10 d after inoculation with different seed soaking.

Shoot elongation was significantly higher with 31×10^3 spores/ml or more

(Table 1). Maximum elongation was with 125×10^3 spores/ml with moderate root growth. Roots were shortest at 500×10^3 spores/ml. Results suggest the fungus may have released fusaric acid at higher spore concentrations. Soaking seeds for 48 h gave highest shoot elongation (Table 2).

To screen rices for Bak resistance, seeds should be soaked for 48 h and inoculated with 125×10^3 spores/ml. *ℳ*

Table 2. Effect of seed soaking duration before Bak inoculation on shoot and root elongation, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Soaking period (h)				
	0	24	48	72	96
	<i>Shoot length (cm)</i>				
Control	7.1	7.2	8.5	8.2	9.8
Inoculated	10.6	12.8	20.6	19.3	18.9
	<i>Root length (cm)</i>				
Control	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.1	4.7
Inoculated	2.6	2.5	4.4	3.8	5.3

Effect of phosphorus on bacterial blight (BB)

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BB at different intensities damages rice in Tamil Nadu. We studied the effect of P on BB. ADT36 was planted and

monocalcium phosphate, diammonium phosphate, and rock phosphate were applied at 0, 22, and 44 kg P/ha, with or without 7.5 t farmyard manure and 10 t green manure/ha.

At flowering, BB incidence was 5 on a 0-9 scale in all treatments. The number of diseased tillers, however, varied among treatments (see table). Plots with monocalcium phosphate, alone or with

organic manures, had more infected tillers than plots with diammonium phosphate or rock phosphate. Plots with diammonium phosphate and green manure had more infected tillers than those with rock phosphate. Treatments with P fertilizer had more grains per tiller, less chaffiness, and higher 1,000-grain weight. *ℳ*

Effect of P fertilizer^a on BB, Aduthurai, India.

P source and parameters	0 kg P/ha			22 kg P/ha			44 kg P/ha		
	No M	With FYM	With GM	No M	With FYM	With GM	No M	With FYM	With GM
Monocalcium phosphate									
BB-infected tillers (no.)	33	27	56	30	24	47	32	40	59
Filled grains per tiller (no.)	59	68	62	61	76	62	62	77	66
Chaff (%)	37	34	32	37	28	34	35	21	38
1,000-grain wt (g)	20	21	22	22	21	33	26	22	33
Diammonium phosphate									
BB-infected tillers (no.)	28	22	31	47	56	47	58	59	53
Filled grains per tiller (no.)	59	66	64	63	78	64	60	85	67
Chaff (%)	36	33	35	31	29	35	26	26	31
1,000-grain wt (g)	21	20	26	22	22	36	26	22	36
Rock phosphate									
BB-infected tillers (no.)	28	27	26	26	32	40	27	33	39
Filled grains per tiller (no.)	66	66	64	66	78	74	69	80	78
Chaff (%)	36	34	35	27	31	33	30	28	31
1,000-grain wt (g)	20	20	25	22	23	35	26	23	35

^a M = organic manure, FYM = farmyard manure, GM = green manure.

Blast (BI) epidemic in Chitwan Valley, Nepal

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is a serious problem in Nepal. In May-Jul

1985, we surveyed farmers' rice nurseries in Chitwan District for BI incidence.

Weather conditions favored BI during the nursery period. Average monthly maximum and minimum temperatures were 30 and 23°C, with 95% average relative humidity. BI infection, calculated by number of infected seedlings, was 75-100% in late Jun in Saradanagar, Rampur, Kiranganj,

Mangalpur, and Ratnanagar. High yielding Masuli was grown in almost all the surveyed areas. *ℳ*

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